

Brain region	LTI quails		STI quails		Statistical values		
	Left-H	Right-H	Left-H	Right-H	Line	Hemisphere	Interaction
Olfactory							
Olfactory bulb	0.139 ± 0.015	0.171 ± 0.014	0.139 ± 0.009	0.169 ± 0.016	F=0.007 p=0.935	F=160.733 p<0.0001	F=0.176 p=0.68
Olfactory tract	0.189 ± 0.009	0.097 ± 0.005	0.204 ± 0.01	<u>0.103 ± 0.007</u>	F=11.837 p=0.003	F=2660.301 p<0.0001	F=5.965 p=0.025
Auditory							
Midbrain vocal area	0.263 ± 0.018	0.251 ± 0.019	0.31 ± 0.028	<u>0.299 ± 0.033</u>	F=19.872 p=0.0003	F=13.801 p=0.002	F=0.0005 p=0.982
Dorsal nucleus of the lateral lemniscus	0.106 ± 0.008	0.097 ± 0.009	0.117 ± 0.012	<u>0.11 ± 0.01</u>	F=8.333 p=0.01	F=44.094 p<0.0001	F=0.395 p=0.538
Olivary cochlear area ##	0.278 ± 0.026	0.283 ± 0.025	0.262 ± 0.016	0.257 ± 0.024			
Visual							
Optic tectum	3.312 ± 0.158	3.33 ± 0.186	<u>3.805 ± 0.204</u>	3.92 ± 0.261	F=35.716 p<0.0001	F=17.085 p=0.0006	F=9.115 p=0.007
Mesencephalic reticular formation	0.14 ± 0.011	0.162 ± 0.012	<u>0.157 ± 0.012</u>	0.187 ± 0.017	F=14.294 p=0.001	F=257.966 p<0.0001	F=7.683 p=0.013
Isthmic nucleus	0.104 ± 0.009	0.102 ± 0.008	<u>0.115 ± 0.01</u>	<u>0.12 ± 0.012</u>	F=12.537 p=0.002	F=1.191 p=0.29	F=6.153 p=0.023
Rotundus nucleus	0.169 ± 0.018	0.184 ± 0.02	<u>0.188 ± 0.016</u>	0.199 ± 0.012	F=5.622 p=0.029	F=99.775 p<0.0001	F=1.8 p=0.196
Periventricular and central stratum	0.586 ± 0.04	0.571 ± 0.038	0.715 ± 0.045	<u>0.7 ± 0.045</u>	F=49.388 p<0.0001	F=12.259 p=0.003	F=0.0001 p=0.993
Dorsal lateral geniculate nucleus	0.021 ± 0.002	0.022 ± 0.002	<u>0.023 ± 0.001</u>	<u>0.024 ± 0.003</u>	F=4.491 p=0.048	F=3.411 p=0.081	F=0.183 p=0.674
Ventral hyperpallium	0.972 ± 0.051	0.791 ± 0.056	1.02 ± 0.061	<u>0.847 ± 0.055</u>	F=4.781 p=0.042	F=567.419 p<0.0001	F=0.271 p=0.609
Tectopretectal tract	0.047 ± 0.006	0.051 ± 0.006	<u>0.057 ± 0.005</u>	0.06 ± 0.005	F=16.646 p=0.0007	F=13.985 p=0.001	F=0.136 p=0.717
Tectotegmental tract	0.022 ± 0.003	0.018 ± 0.003	0.025 ± 0.002	<u>0.021 ± 0.002</u>	F=11.538 p=0.003	F=54.351 p<0.0001	F=0.248 p=0.624
Isthmotectal tract	0.008 ± 0.001	0.005 ± 0.001	0.011 ± 0.001	<u>0.006 ± 0.001</u>	F=21.219 p=0.0002	F=169.043 p<0.0001	F=4.137 p=0.057
Tectal gray #	0.103 ± 0.006	0.088 ± 0.009	0.112 ± 0.009	0.095 ± 0.009			
Tectotegmental decussation #	0.034 ± 0.002	0.03 ± 0.002	0.037 ± 0.004	0.033 ± 0.002			
Entopallium	0.681 ± 0.058	0.628 ± 0.045	0.626 ± 0.038	<u>0.565 ± 0.029</u>	F=9.804 p=0.006	F=105.449 p<0.0001	F=0.467 p=0.503
Optic tract	0.628 ± 0.07	0.681 ± 0.08	0.61 ± 0.041	0.655 ± 0.045	F=0.69 p=0.417	F=47.055 p<0.0001	F=0.372 p=0.549
Oculomotor nerve	0.063 ± 0.007	0.066 ± 0.006	0.063 ± 0.008	0.069 ± 0.008	F=0.353 p=0.56	F=4.876 p=0.04	F=0.661 p=0.427
Isthmo optic tract	0.012 ± 0.001	0.004 ± 0.001	0.012 ± 0.002	0.005 ± 0.001	F=0.179 p=0.677	F=778.645 p<0.0001	F=2.167 p=0.158
Mesopallium	0.729 ± 0.06	0.756 ± 0.06	<u>0.829 ± 0.067</u>	0.853 ± 0.092	F=10.054 p=0.005	F=15.019 p=0.001	F=0.043 p=0.839
Auditory parts of the nidopallium	0.773 ± 0.089	0.756 ± 0.07	0.745 ± 0.044	0.723 ± 0.061	F=1.115 p=0.305	F=3.211 p=0.09	F=0.041 p=0.842
Auditory Field L2	0.145 ± 0.026	0.145 ± 0.025	0.131 ± 0.013	0.131 ± 0.017	F=2.424 p=0.137	F=0.006 p=0.938	F=0.003 p=0.954
Basal somatosensory nucleus of the nidopallium #	0.058 ± 0.004	0.066 ± 0.003	0.059 ± 0.007	0.067 ± 0.007			
Basal nucleus of Meynert #	0.152 ± 0.009	0.146 ± 0.011	0.154 ± 0.007	0.138 ± 0.007			

Diffuse pretectal area #	0.068 ± 0.007	0.07 ± 0.006	0.088 ± 0.009	0.085 ± 0.01			
Interhemispheric regions							
Brain region	LTI quail	STI quail	Statistical values (Line effect)				
Optic chiasm	1.415 ± 0.116	1.39 ± 0.072	t=0.561, p=0.582				
Supraoptic decussation	0.245 ± 0.026	0.241 ± 0.014	t=0.4245, p=0.676				
Cochlear decussation	<u>0.132 ± 0.012</u>	0.119 ± 0.01	t=2.4964, p=0.0225				